

A STUDY ON STUDENT PERCEPTION TOWARDS HOSTEL FACILITIES IN DHANALAKSHIMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE (AUTONOMOUS), PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

Though now a day's Hostel life is much essential for students but still there are some restrictions. There are many complications in the hostel life. For this purpose, we investigate the student's satisfaction with hostel facilities. During the analysis, the student's feedback for the hostel facilities for the year 2018 and 2020 were taken and the data has been collected from the Director Management Information System (MIS). Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze and shows the overall students satisfaction regarding hostel facilities. The results indicated that there is strong evidence of significance relationship between the results of the parameters (Food Quality, Cleanliness, Water supply and First aid) services. The null hypothesis is accepted except for only two parameters of Shah Abdul Latif, Shaikh Sindhi and Bakhtawar hostels.

Key Words: Hostel Life, Facilities, Students

Introduction:

Hostel is another home for the students. The institute provides individual room with attached bathroom to the students with separate areas of residence for Males and Females. Five new well-furnished and aesthetically designed hostels have been constructed with a view to provide best possible facilities to the students. A hostel is a form of low-cost, short-term shared sociable lodging where students can rent a bed, usually a bunk bed in a dormitory, with shared use of a lounge and sometimes a cot. Rooms can be mixed or single and have private or shared bathrooms. Private rooms may also be available, but the property must offer dormitories to be considered a hostel. Hostels are popular forms of lodging for backpackers, cycle, and gap year students. They are part of the sharing economy. Benefits of hostels include lower costs and opportunities to meet people from all over the world, find travel partners, and share travel ideas.

Statement of the Problem:

With the increasing need of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College to implement a learn system, and students Hostel Facilities will be done to determine how students impacts changes.

Scope of Study:

- The study only helps to identify the student's satisfaction on hostel facilities. These studies applicable only on Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.
- The scope of the study analysis of hostel which ever analysis of all level of information. The study was conducted to assess the impact of hostel facilities on students' academic performance. Three hundred students who are actively using hostel facilities are the respondents of the study.
- It was conducted during the summer semester of academic year 2020. The study limited only on variables of hostel facilities that assumed that has effects of respondents' academic performance.
- These variables are respondents' access to study time, hostel spent time, perception on hostel facilities, and their frequency of using it.

Needs and Importance of Study:

- The food you provide should be nutritious. People live in hostels leaving their home behind to pursue better future. They are paying you. You should understand your responsibility. If your profit is less, increase the rent. Most of the females are anemic. Make sure you do not contribute in the same. Green vegetables, proper pulses and fruits should be provided. Once a week egg, milk should also be included without fail in the menu. However, this point goes for boys' hostel as well apart from the fact that most of them are not anemic
- The very first thing is that the hostel should have proper sanitation facility. This is very important. The washroom, sanitary napkin disposal facility should be up to the mark. You should keep in mind that girls are more prone to such infections.
- Other than these, other points are same for any hostel,
- Well lit rooms.
- Proper ventilation.
- Cupboard

- Table-chair in the room
- No overcrowding. Please maintain the occupant- space ratio.

Objectives of the Study:

- These are used to identified imperfection of students
- Hostel is available for students from long distance to stay away from college hostel
- To provide a safe, secure and clean accommodation for the hostellers which will ensure smooth learning and good health.
- To provide all required facilities and commodities to all the hostellers at allotted rooms.
- To ensure that the students are able to devote adequate time to their studies.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is the specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic. In a research paper, the methodology section allows the reader to critically evaluate a study's overall validity and reliability.

Sampling Technique:

Random sampling method is used for conducting the study.

Population - 1567

Sample Size - 110

Method of Data Collection:

Primary data collection has been taken for this research study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected a fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation
- ANOVA

Research Hypothesis:

Definition of Hypothesis:

A hypothesis can be defined as a logically conjectured relationship between two or more variable expressed in the form of testable statement.

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

Null Hypothesis is formulated only to test whether there is any relationship between variables related to the problem being studied. Usually the null hypothesis usually is formed as a negative statement.

Alternate Hypothesis (H₁):

Alternate Hypothesis (H₁) is a statement, which is accepted after the null hypothesis is rejected based on the test result. The alternate hypothesis usually is formed as a positive statement.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study only selected for 110 respondents.
- The study on college students for Engineering College students only.
- Time is major constraints for collect the data.
- The study conducted only on limited period.
- Lack of availability of secondary data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Respondent Based on Fell About Your Hostel:

Particular	Number of Responder	Percentage
Excellent	10	9
Average	67	61
Good	33	30
Total	110	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

From the above chart we found the result of respondents, 9% Of the respondents are having excellent, 61% Of respondents are having a Average, 30% of respondents are having good.

Chart:

Respondent Based on Fell About Your Hostel:

Correlation:

Feel About Your Hostel	10	67	33	110
Is There Study Hours in Your Hostel	85	7	18	110

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
10	85	100	7225	850
67	7	4489	49	469
33	18	1089	324	594
$\Sigma X=110$	$\Sigma Y=110$	$\Sigma X^2=5678$	$\Sigma Y^2=7598$	$\Sigma XY=1913$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}}$$

$$\text{Answer} = \frac{1913 - \frac{110 \times 110}{110}}{\sqrt{5678 - \frac{110^2}{110}} \sqrt{7598 - \frac{110^2}{110}}} = 1.4491$$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between the Satisfaction towards the clarification of doubt and attitude of staff towards the academic result.

Chi-Square Test:

Grade	4	5	6	7	8	Total
Strongly Agree	10	12	5	5	2	34
Agree	7	11	15	4	1	38
Neutral	3	1	4	6	2	16
Disagree	2	2	6	2	1	13
Strongly Disagree	0	2	5	1	1	9
Total	22	28	35	18	7	110

Calculations:

O _i	E _i	(O _i - E _i)	(O _i - E _i) ²	(O _i - E _i)/ E _i
10	6.8	3.2	10.24	1.5
12	8.65	3.5	12.25	1.4
5	10.8	-5.8	33.64	3.1
5	5.5	-0.8	0.64	0.1
12	2.1	9.9	98.01	46.6
7	7.6	-0.6	0.36	0.04
11	9.6	1.4	1.96	0.2
15	12	3	9	0.75
4	6.2	-2.2	4.84	0.78
1	2.4	-1.6	2.56	1.1
3	3.2	0.2	0.04	0.32

1	4	-3	9	2.25
4	5	-1	1	0.2
6	2.6	3.4	11.56	4.4
2	1	1	1	0.9
2	2.6	-0.6	0.36	0.13
2	3.3	-1.3	1.69	0.5
6	4.1	1.9	3.61	0.88
2	2.1	-0.1	0.01	4.74
1	0.8	0.2	0.04	0.05
0	1.8	-1.8	3.24	1.8
2	2.2	-0.2	0.04	0.01
5	2.8	2.2	4.84	1.72
1	1.4	0.4	0.16	0.11
1	0.5	0.5	0.25	0.5
TOTAL				74.03

Chi-Square Test Formula:

$$X^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$$

O_i = Observed Frequency
 E_i = Expected Frequency

Chi-Square Table:

Degree of Freedom = (r-1) (c-1)
 Level of significance= 5%
 Degree of freedom in this case is 12
 Calculated value = 74.0
 Table value = 12.9.

The calculated value is greater than the table value. So we are rejecting the null hypothesis

Interpretation:

Since $X^2 > X^2_{0.05}$.
 So Null Hypothesis is rejected.

Findings:

- 61% of respondents are average fell about the hostel

Suggestions:

- This study considers the students’ residential satisfaction as expressed by the students based on their satisfaction with the hostel facilities in relation to their needs, requirements and experiences.
- The students satisfaction level were measured based on the bedroom, bathroom, common room and other services within the hostel precincts.
- The result shows that the students are dissatisfied with these facilities as they are grossly inadequate and as such do not meet with the intended purposes of their provision.
- This therefore implies that the on campus housing program in the school is not effective enough as the available facilities cannot cater for the student population and as such necessary steps should be taken to address these inadequacies by engaging private developers such that a partnership scheme is evolved to provide better on campus housing scheme which will meet the growing needs of the students.

Conclusion:

The result of this study is also in line with the result of Amole (2009) which was also carried out in Nigeria showing a level of dissatisfaction of the students with the hostel facilities. From the above investigated study, it is concluded that there is strong significance relationship between the results of the parameters (Food quality, Cleanliness, Water supply and First aid services) for the students often hostels.

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